

COPERATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY (CSR): ANALYSIS OF HEALTH CARE INTERVENTION PROGRAMMES OF EXXON MOBIL IN AKWA IBOM STATE BETWEEN 2001 AND 2016

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ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility has been an issue of contention in Akwa Ibom State and the entire Niger Delta. The main objective of this study was to assess community intervention programmes of Exxon Mobil Nigeria in the area of health care interventions in oil producing areas in Eket Federal Constituency of Akwa Ibom State. Stakeholders' theory of Corporate Social Responsibility provided the theoretical anchorage for this study. Cross sectional research design was adopted in this study because it was flexible enough to accommodate multiple qualitative data collection techniques. Emerging from the findings of the study is that Mobil producing Nigeria or Exxonmobil has participated in sustainable development in Akwa Ibom State as part of their corporate social responsibility (CSR) through health care intervention programmes in different host communities, but so much is still expected. Though some study participants have expressed dissatisfaction and described their impact as being in significant. Based on study, the following recommendations were made which include that Mobil Producing Nigeria should continue on her commitment to corporate social responsibility to her host communities in order to maintain peaceful co-existence and sustainable economic productivity among others findings..

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, ExxonMobil, Healthcare, and Intervention Programmes

INTRODUCTION

Corporate engagement with society, also termed corporate social responsibility (CSR), has become a commonly used term in contemporary society and refers to one process by which an organization expresses and develops its 'corporate culture' and social consciousness (Rupp *et al*, 2006 and Calderon, 2011). CSR has been receiving lots of attention from various backgrounds of researchers worldwide (Ismail 2011), it has attracted a

great deal of attention over the past decade (Zu & Song 2008) and according to some researchers, has gathered great momentum over the past number of years and is now regarded to be at its most prevalent (Sweeney 2007). Therefore business leaders, government officials, and academics are focusing more and more attention on the concept of “corporate social responsibility” (Reinhardt *et al* 2008). Almost all corporate websites/policies/reports talk about their endeavors for CSR, which has become a way of ensuring that the organization is fulfilling all the obligations towards society and thus is eligible for the license to operate. It assures that the organization can grow on sustainable basis (Sharma *et al.* 2009). There are also societal pressures with respect to social issues such as human rights and the environment on the corporations and CSR is widely regarded as the response of corporations to this pressure (Miller & Guthrie 2007) and according to Bénabou & Tirole (2009), responding to such pressure, business leaders, governments and academics are now also emphasizing the notion of CSR.

CSR, which was previously referred to as social responsibility (SR) and today some often call it as corporate responsibility (CR) (Ismail, 2011) over the years has gained unprecedented momentum in business and public debate and has become a strategic issue crossing the departmental boundaries, and affecting the way in which a company does business (Sharma *et al.* 2009). Maç, & Çalış, (2011), referring some studies, expressed that there is an impressive history associated with the evolution of the concept of CSR although it is stated that roots of the concepts and implementations could be traced back to prehistoric times, generally works on its evolution start with 1950s and 1990s are defined with its popularity and development of similar themes. In 1990s, increasing number of corporate social responsibility reports, standards and code of conduct show the interest for CSR. But Rupp *et al* (2006) asserted that corporate engagement with society, also termed Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) mired in a definitional debate dating back several decades.

According to Sriramesh *et al* (2007), Muhammad, Ahmed Khan, Ahmed, & Mehfooz Ali(2012) offered one of the earliest definitions seeing CSR since then, the field has evolved assuming different names such as corporate social responsiveness (in the 1970s) and corporate social performance (in the 1980s). This evolution also reflects an increase in awareness in important areas of action and performance that the early definitions had overlooked. Hopkins (2004) is of the view that until 1970s, despite regulation and legislation, business continued largely along an autonomous path, ignoring its critics and listening only to its shareholders, to whom it felt somewhat responsible. But the decade of the 1960s was to be a period of enlightenment for many. Citizens were distrustful of government, business and the undefined “establishment”. Consumers had grown suspicious of adulterants in their food and dangerous defects in the products they bought. People were becoming aware of the fragile nature of the earth's ecology, while simultaneously becoming more cognizant of human rights.

Abd Rahim *et al* (2011) quoted Carroll (1979) who expressed that CSR has been evolving as early as the 1930s. But Calderon (2011) quoted from book of Zerk (2006) who discussed a more contemporary evolution from the international legal precedents starting visionary employee compensation policies to more complex examples of corporate citizenship in recent years. In his book Zerk, quoted numerous examples of Corporate initiatives that can be categorized as CSR for instance, in 1914 Henry Ford's employees

received higher salaries in 8 hour working days, when the industry standard was 9 hour work days, and in 1935 Johnson & Johnson published a document titled “Try Reality” where the company defined its responsibility towards different groups of society, an initiative that was followed by a publication of a company-wide “Credo” in 1994 that outlined the corporation's ethical and social goals which made it a precursor of many modern Codes of Ethics.

In CSR, the central issue is the appropriate role of business that overlaps, almost completely, with its reference area (Reinhardt et al, 2008; BORZA, 2011) and now business organizations have waked up to the need for being committed towards CSR (Sharma *et al.* 2009) because the role of businesses in society is no longer focused on creating wealth alone but is also focused on acting responsibly towards stakeholders (Abd Rahim, *et al.*, 2011).

Wilenius (2005), describes Corporate Social Responsibility as a point of convergence of various initiatives aimed at ensuring socio-economic development of the community as a whole in a credible and sustainable manner. Nwosu (2017) had earlier pointed that shareholders and other stakeholders by and large, within the whole community see Corporate Social Responsibility as a major concern of communities, governments, and civil society organizations in Nigeria and is expected to be integral to industry today as a password to not only overcome competition, but to ensure sustainable growth. Corporate Social Responsibility in reality is the alignment of industry operations with social values. It takes into account the interests of stakeholders in the company's business policies and actions. It focuses on the social, environmental and financial success of a company – the so called “triple bottom line” (the social, environmental and financial success of a company) with the aim of achieving social development alongside business success (Nwosu, 2017). There are several types of role and scope that multinational corporations can play in conjunction with various local and international organisations such as local government, the United Nation agencies and Non-governmental organizations in the host countries, and local social groups which most prominent contributions from multinational corporations to the host community is corporate social responsibility (Pimpa, 2011).

Aaron and Patrick (2008) observed that communities where these multinational corporations companies operate seem to experience decay and underdevelopment. The decaying experiences of the host communities create the demands for multinational corporations' Corporate Social Responsibility. Utting (2005) asserts that the negative impacts of these corporate activities, especially by the multinationals have been observed in ethical issues such as environmental health, safety, disregard for local content, failure to promote workers participation through consultation, failure to develop vocational skills and life-long training, climate change, corruption, and human rights abuses. Nwosu (2017) observed that there is little effort by companies operating in communities to control and reduce the impact of their activities on people and the environment. Frynas (2005) observed that one sector of business that makes strong claims to business ethics and/or corporate social responsibility, human rights, employee rights, stakeholders' rights, environmental protection, community relations, transparency, anti-corruption, product stewardship principles, and codes of practice is the Oil and Gas sector. With these claims, the multinational corporations are facing the challenge of planning and executing their corporate social responsibility to meet the sustainable development objectives.

The 1987 Brundtland Commission's report, *Our Common Future*, defines sustainable development as “Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the

ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” Using this definition, the U.N. built a sustainable development framework with three pillars: economic, environmental and social (Mutunga *et tal.*, 2012). The overall goal of sustainable development (SD) is the long-term stability of the economy and environment; this can be achievable through the integration and acknowledgement of economic, environmental, and social concerns throughout the decision making process. The key principle of sustainable development underlying all others is the integration of environmental, social, and economic concerns into all aspects of decision making. The Oil and Gas Multi-National Corporations are assumed to be active and playing leadership roles in developing good corporate practices and codes of conduct in the workplace and engagement with different facets of society (Nwosu, 2017). This is an indication of multinational corporations' commitment toward inclusion of the processes of achieving sustainable development in their practices. Tuodolo (2007) argues that the involvement of Shell, Chevron, Texaco, Exxon Mobil, Occidental, Total Fina Elf, etc in the United Nations' Global Compact, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), the Sullivan Principle, the Voluntary Principles on Security and Human Rights, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Dow Jones Sustainability Index, and the World Summits on Sustainable Development in Rio de Janeiro and Johannesburg are some instances.

Nwosu, (2015) argues that their footprints can be seen in developing countries in the transfer of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), skills and technology, as major employers of labour, and accounting for a large proportion of state revenue. They have contributed to development in Nigeria via programmes in education, health, commerce, agriculture, transport, construction, etc. Despite these achievements, the Oil Transnational Corporations in Nigeria's Niger Delta region in general and Akwa Ibom State in particular have been the target of several negative anti-corporate campaigns in the last three decades. The rural communities have consistently doubted the genuine existence and adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility by the Oil Multinational Corporations (Nwosu, 2015).

Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited (MPN), operator of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC)/MPN Joint Venture is an upstream subsidiary company of Exxon Mobil Corporation, a global leader in oil and gas business. Mobil Producing Nigeria has recorded clear successes and made visible contributions to Nigeria's oil and gas industry and the world energy market ((NNPC/MPN, 2010). Together with NNPC, its Joint Venture partner, MPN has over the years continued to maintain very active and supportive community development programmes of which Akwa Ibom and Rivers States are major beneficiaries. This has helped to create relative stability and social progress in the operational communities in particular and the Nigerian nation in general (NNPC/MPN, 2010). There have been lots of blames by concerned parties that Mobil Producing Nigeria are only out to suck dry the natural resources and human resources in Akwa Ibom State without giving back to the people, social agencies, government agencies, Non-governmental agencies and host communities against the achievement of sustainable development goals. Since it is difficult to quantify satisfaction level of the people, it is difficult to say whether or not Mobil Producing Nigeria has been able to satisfy the yearnings and aspirations as compared to the high level of outcry for compensations by the host communities in terms of its business or corporate social responsibility despite the efforts on the part of Mobil Producing Nigeria and lack of developmental plan on the part of the host communities.

Corporate Social Responsibility has been an issue of contention in the Niger Delta and the persistence in demand for more of it from the host community is an indication that the people of the region are not satisfied (Imoh-Ita, 2015). Eze (2011) as cited in Imoh-Ita (2015) pointed out that Corporate Social Responsibility is a core value for community engagement interface on oil exploration activity and argued that lack of genuine community engagement interface by Transnational Corporations in oil activities is the major problem of Niger Delta crises. According to Imoh-Ita (2015), Exxon Mobil in her quest to develop the host communities has identified, supported and operated a planned and sustainable programme of community development in Akwa Ibom state. Exxon Mobil has made great contributions in the area of physical infrastructure such as road construction, water, electricity, health facilities among others. In his study aimed at assessing the Corporate Social Responsibility of Mobil Producing Unlimited and Julius Berger Nigeria Limited in Akwa Ibom State, Imoh-Ita (2015) asserts that people in the Exxon Mobil host communities have benefited from the Corporate Social Responsibility projects provided for them.

Studies have been carried out on Corporate Social Responsibility of Oil and Gas multinational corporations in Niger Delta. Many of these studies focus on the agitations, claims, exploitations of the host communities by multinational corporations, destruction of livelihood of the people of the host communities, and inadequate participation of multinational corporations in governmental and non-governmental programmes toward the development of the host communities and the states. There is little scholarly effort made in assessing the Corporate Social Responsibility of these multinational corporations in terms of their community intervention sustainable development programmes and contributions to the entire economy of the nation through revenue generations to the federal government. Against this background, this study seeks to assess community intervention programmes of Exxon Mobil Nigeria toward sustainable development of host communities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria between 2001 and 2016.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Stakeholders' Theory of Corporate Social Responsibility.

The Stakeholders' Theory of Corporate Social Responsibility developed by Hashimu and Ango (2012) represents a softening of (if not a fundamental challenge to) shareholder theory. The theory according to them recognises the fact that most, if not all firms have a large and integrated set of stakeholders, to which they have an obligation and responsibility. The stakeholders' theory is relevant for this study considering that the needs of the people who serve as stakeholders require being satisfied in order for a cordial relationship to exist between the company and their host. As stakeholders to the multinational corporations, they ought to benefit from them by way of the provision of some social and economic facilities to cushion the effects of their operations on the environment.

METHODOLOGY

Cross-sectional survey research method was adopted for this study because the research work covers a large population of some of the oil producing communities. For purposes of application, the method used was the sampling approach, that is, the simple random sampling. Hence interview schedule as the main instrument was used through personal interviews which were all properly validated to authenticate the information

gathered. The primary data were obtained by means of interview schedule administered to the respondents and the secondary data were collected through published materials. The interview schedule was structured in such a way to answer questions in line with the objectives of the study. The study was conducted in Ibeno, Eket, Esit Eket, and Onna local government areas within Eket Federal Constituency of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Data collected from fieldwork was analysed thematically with excerpts from narratives of study participants. The key variable served as a theme for analysis.

FINDINGS

ExxonMobil Healthcare Intervention Programme 2001 - 2016

Health is wealth they say, and ExxonMobil in a joint venture with Nigeria National Petroleum Co-operation NNPC has been involve in supporting health programmes in many ways including construction of health centres, provision of electricity to health institutions, supply of potable water to health centres, building of health officers' quarters, salary subvention to health personnel, training of health staff and the supply of health equipment. ExxonMobil according to the majority of the study respondents has provided health facilities in Mkpanak in Ibeno; Iko Eket, Effoi in Eket, Ikwe in Onna, nurses' quarters at Mkpanak clinic, and others. One of the female respondents from Mkpanak in Ibeno Local Government Area in her statement reported that;

We have been thankful to God for making us partakers of those who have oil and oil companies in their lands because of the works Mobil has performed in our community. In health, Mobil has contributed to the improvement of health in Mkpanak which we can testify. For example, they built health centre, built clinic with nurses' quarters, provides electricity to the health centre with portable water. So we can say thank you to Mobil especially we women.

According to data acquired through published source of Mobil Producing Nigeria MPN (n. d.), MPN has construct health centres in Eket Local Government Area. Some of these health centres are located at Iko Eket, Effoi, and Eket. Mobil has contributed to the development of the Nursing School in Eket. In line with the published data, gathered data through interview showed that MPN has contributed greatly to health care development in Eket Local Government Area. The majority of the study respondents from Eket agreed that they have felt the presence of Mobil in Eket Local Government Area as a whole in the area of health care services delivery. One of the male respondents, in his narrative attributed high level of health care service delivery in Eket to the contributions of Mobil producing Nigeria (MPN).

According to a respondent (Male, aged 43):

Eket people are enjoying good health care service delivery. This is because Mobil has contributed to building health care centres in Eket, rebuilding old wards and building new ones at Emmanuel hospital, Eket. Mobil have provided portable water and electricity to these health care centres and hospitals in Eket.

Women and children have benefited from Exxon Mobil through the provision of

facilities for affordable health care services delivery in Eket Local Government Area through the contributions of MPN in the area. Most of the study respondents in their narratives agreed that through Mobil provisions and contributions to the health sector of Eket, the women and children have been enjoying good access to available health care services in Eket Local Government Area. But so many are of the views that Exxon Mobil have not done well considering the huge profit they make from oil exploration in the area.

One of the female respondents (Aged, 56) in her narratives reported that;

We as women are not grateful to Mobil. Because Mobil have not done enough in terms of giving back to their host communities. T Mobil should take bold steps to make good health care services available and accessible for women and children. If you go to Emmanuel hospital or any of the health care centres in Eket you will see it by yourself these health facilities lack state of the art facilities depicting the presence of Mobil in these communities. Our women are sometimes scared to go to the hospitals due to high cost of hospital bills. Apart from inadequate staffing, lack of equipment, insufficient buildings, drugs and workers who display poor attitude to their work ethics, patients are often made to wait for long hours before being attended to.

In Onna Local Government Area, Mobil Producing Nigeria (MPN) has registered their presence in the health care delivery sector of the local government area. It was gathered by the researcher through interview that MPN has contributed to the health care delivery in Onna. The majority of the study respondents agreed that the people of Onna have benefitted from the health care community intervention programmes of Mobil Producing Nigeria.

One of the male respondents in his report stated that:

Mobil has tried for us especially in the area of health care delivery and drugs availability. We now have health centre at Ikwe solely built by Mobil Producing Nigeria for the people of Ikwe and its environs. Now our women and some of us men can now have access to health care services delivery closer to us than before. We do not have to travel a distance for health care services. The Ikwe health centre built by Mobil is our own and we are grateful to Mobil, though we want them to expand and make it a full hospital so that we can also have big doctors coming to stay here at Ikwe to attend to our health needs.

Another study respondent, a female, in her narratives reported that:

We thank Mobil Producing Nigeria for their concerned toward our health. They have tried to contribute to health care services delivery in Onna Local Government Area. We now have access to free drugs and in some cases free medical treatments because of drug availability and treatment make possible by Mobil. There treatments that we do receive free here in Onna which are

provided by Mobil, and some of the treatments I don't think some of us would have had money to pay for such treatment and the quality of experts that do come to render these treatments. So to me, I am grateful to God for touching Mobil's management to undertake such programmes in order to reach the poor or most of the rural community people.

The presence of Mobil Producing Nigeria in Esit Eket Local Government Area was a little bit different from other local government areas in term of health intervention programmes. Gathered information through interview of study respondents by the researcher showed that Mobil Producing Nigeria within the years (2001 – 2010) under study did not do much in term of health care intervention programmes in the local government area. Most of the study respondents show ill-tempered responses regarding their place in the scale of preference within Mobil producing Nigeria Co-operate Social Responsibility. They lamented the absence of health care centre by Mobil as received by other neighbouring local government areas. The majority of the study respondents complained that between 2001 and 2010, said, they did not receive as much as health care intervention projects compared to other communities.

One of the male respondents (Aged, 35) in his responses reported that:

I know that Mobil have been trying to help in so many ways in our place, but within these years (2001 -2010), we have not seen Mobil come in to build health centre or renovate one in our place. But we are hearing and some of us have seen and visited the ones they have built in our neighbouring local government areas for the people over there. We believe that God will touch them to do more for us in term of health care in the coming years because we are part of the oil producing and hosting local government areas.

Another male respondent (Aged, 53) in his narratives stated that;

If it is from 2001 to 2010, we cannot point to one health care project in my community or in the entire local government area apart from that sometimes in 2002 we heard that they sent some drugs and health equipment to the Cottage Hospital at Ekpene obo. To other part of the local government area, we have not receive any intervention programme from Mobil in term of health care or medical services as we used to hear from other local government within those years.

Mobil Producing Nigeria (MPN) has contributed to the health care development of the host communities through health care intervention programmes. These were gathered by the researcher through interview of study respondents across the 4 chosen local government areas of Akwa Ibom State. The majority of the respondents agreed that Mobil has contributed in diverse measures toward health development through building and renovation of health care centres, empowering existing hospital with equipment and provision of drugs, vaccines and social amenities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is that Mobil producing Nigeria or Exxonmobil has participated in community development in Akwa Ibom State as part of their corporate social responsibility (CSR) through health care intervention programmes. The majority of the study participants agreed that they have benefited from health care intervention programmes of Exxonmobil. These benefits according to findings shows that Mobil producing Nigeria or Exxonmobil has, as part of corporate social responsibilities has built health care centres, renovate hospitals, built nurses and doctors' quarters, donate drugs and vaccines, contribute in training of medical personnel, sponsored medical treatments, and involved in special health care programmes for their host communities. These findings have credence from Idemudia (2009) postulation that as part of its Integrated Community Development Programme (ICDP), Mobil Producing Nigeria partners with the New Nigerian Foundation (NNF), an affiliate of Citizens International of Boston, U.S.A. to prevent and treat malaria. In 2001, Mobil Producing Nigeria entered into an agreement with New Nigerian Foundation (NNF) to facilitate and promote community health services for sustainable development. MPN provides the funds, while New Nigerian Foundation (NNF) implements the project on behalf of Mobil Producing Nigeria in 14 communities across Akwa Ibom and River States. Funds provided by Mobil Producing Nigeria are paid into a drug revolving account on a quarterly basis and are managed by the Community Health Committee (CHC) with the assistance of Non-Governmental Organization (MPNCN, 2002 in Idemudia, 2009).

Mbat, *et al*, (2013) also gives credence to the findings by stating that Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited has donated medicines to various health institutions in Akwa Ibom State. It has also built and equipped a health centre at Mkpanak, a village adjacent to its operation terminal. The following Health Institutions in Akwa Ibom State here benefited from Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited; Emmanuel General Hospital, Eket, St. Luke's Hospital, Anua, General Hospital, Iquita Oron, Mary Slessor Hospital, Itu, Psychiatric Hospital, Eket, General Hospital, Ikot Ekpene, General Hospital, Etinan, Mercy Hospital, Abak, General Hospital, Ikpe, Government Medical Centre, Akai Ubium, General Hospital, Ikot Okoro, Infectious Diseases Hospital, Ikot Ekpene, General Hospital, Ikot Abasi, Leprosy Hospital, Ekpene Obom, Etinan, Primary Health Centre, Uquo, Methodist Hospital, Ituk Mbang, Health Centre Oron, and Motherless Babies Home, Idung Iniang Eket.

CONCLUSION

Community intervention programmes of Exxon Mobil Nigeria are parts of Mobil Producing Nigeria corporate social responsibility (CSR) to their host communities in Eket Federal Constituency, Akwa Ibom State. Corporate social responsibilities (CSR) of Mobil producing Nigeria are planned and well executed community intervention projects toward community development among the host communities of Exxonmobil Nigeria. As part of these responsibilities, between 2001 and 2010, Mobil Producing Nigeria has embarked on several community intervention programmes which have alleviate the suffering and the living standard of the people of their host communities in Eket Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State. Eket, Esit Eket, Ibeno and Onna local government areas have benefitted from Mobil Producing Nigeria community intervention programmes which include; water

projects, health care projects,

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made from the findings of this research:

1. Mobil Producing Nigeria should continue on her commitment to corporate social responsibility to her host communities in order to maintain peaceful co-existence and sustainable economic productivity.
2. Host communities as stakeholders should as a matter of need maintain cordial relationship with Mobil Producing Nigeria for smooth and continuous benefits of both parties.
3. Government of Akwa Ibom State should intervene where necessary to help in creating a platform for mutual understanding of the multinational corporation and her host communities through educational programmes to such community members.

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